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#1

(((((chronic OR lung OR pulmonary OR respirat* OR airway* OR airflow*) NEAR/3 obstruct*) OR copd) OR (parkinson* OR "paralysis agitans") OR (((multipl* OR disseminated OR insular) NEAR/3 scleros*) OR "chariot disease" OR demyelinat*) OR ((hip* OR femur* OR femoral OR trochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant* OR subtrochant* OR intracapsular* OR extracapsular*) NEAR/5

S ▼

Limits

48492

(Word variations have been searched)

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#2

(((((step* OR stride*) NEAR/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR length* OR width* OR frequenc* OR rate* OR rhythm* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr* OR count* OR number* OR distance* OR cadence*)) OR (((swing* OR stance* OR "single support" OR "double support") NEAR/2 (time* OR duration* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr*)) OR (((spatiotemporal OR "spatio-temporal") NEAR/2 (parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic*)) OR (((gait OR walk* OR ambulat*) NEAR/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR cadence* OR pace* OR rhythm* OR volume* OR bout* OR duration* OR distance* OR intensit* OR variabilit* OR asymmetr* OR symmetr* OR parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic* OR assess* OR examin* OR analys* OR batter* OR

S ▼

Limits

21157

(Word variations have been searched)

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#3

#1 AND #2

Limits

3756

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#4

#1 AND #2

Limits

3594

with Cochrane Library publication date from Jan 1999 to Dec 2019

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+

#5

Type a search term or use the S or MeSH buttons to

S ▼

MeSH ▼

Limits

N/A

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